

Oxygen, a gasocrine signal, is likely sensed via gasoreceptors such as soluble adenylyate cyclase

Savani Anbalagan^{1,2}

¹Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Biology, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznań, Poland.

²Correspondence

E-mail: savani.anbalagan@amu.edu.pl

Tel: +48 61 829 5905

Running title: sAC, an oxygen-sensing gasoreceptor?

Keywords: Oxygen sensing, gasocrine, gasoreceptor

Understanding how organisms communicate is a fundamental question in biology and marks an evolutionarily important milestone. Organisms largely communicate via gas-based gasocrine, light-based photocrine, sound-based sonocrine, mineral/metal-based metallochrine, water-based aquacrine, and thermal radiation-based thermocrine signaling.¹ Due to the importance of gasocrine signaling for biotic life, how organisms can sense gasocrine signals such as O₂ (oxygen) via O₂-sensing protein gasoreceptors (or sensors such as DosP, FixL, and GCY-35) has been largely identified only in microorganisms and the invertebrate *C. elegans*.^{2,3} Even though O₂ is also one of the gasocrine signals, to the best of my knowledge and according to few other leading experts on oxygen-sensing, how mammalian organisms sense O₂ *per se* is largely unknown.^{4,5} Both I and others have independently proposed the existence of heme-based O₂- gasoreceptors or sensors in mammals based on different scientific arguments.^{2,6,7} Leishmania adenylate cyclase-like protein (LMJF_28_0090, a globin-coupled heme-containing adenylate cyclase or HemAC-Lm) is one of the eukaryotic O₂-sensing gasoreceptors (or sensor) whose activity increases by 20-fold at 50 μM O₂.⁸ Although human sAC (soluble adenylate cyclase) activity is affected by bicarbonate and Ca²⁺ binding, whether human sAC activity is also regulated by NO and O₂-binding via heme domain is unclear.^{9,10} In my opinion, as NO and GTP very likely preceded O₂ and ATP respectively during evolution, receptors for O₂ would have potentially evolved from NO receptor such as sGC, as mutations of only three residues in sGC can convert it to a cAMP-producing sAC.¹¹⁻¹³ Experiments that tested sAC-O₂ binding under argon environment warrant reevaluation to truly assess the role of O₂-binding. Flushing with argon to displace sAC-bound O₂ may not have the same effect as exposing to variable concentrations of O₂ unless argon can truly compete with the O₂-binding site in the heme domain and displace O₂.⁹ Moreover, mice lacking either of the O₂-gasoreceptor candidates, sAC or androglobin, exhibit infertility due to dysfunctional sperm.^{9,14-16} If sAC variants with heme domain or androglobin activity are affected due to O₂-binding, and if mutations that perturb O₂-binding lead to altered enzyme activity and sperm defects, then both sAC and androglobin are likely O₂-sensing gasoreceptors or sensors. This would provide definite proof of gasocrine signaling between O₂-producing organisms and mammals.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Savani Anbalagan: conceptualization, writing of the original draft, and review and editing.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author thank Zofia Szweykowska-Kulinska (Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Biology, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznan, Poland) for allowing him to attend her inspiring lectures on molecular evolution. The author also thank Agnieszka Chacinska (Past affiliation: Centre of New Technologies, University of Warsaw, Regenerative Mechanisms for Health - International Research Agendas Programme and current affiliation: International Institute of Molecular Machines and Mechanisms, Polish Academy of Science, Warsaw, Poland) for suggesting him to attend the 44th FEBS Congress meeting. The author thanks Annie Beuve (Rutgers New Jersey Medical School, USA) for her e-discussion. The author is supported by National Science Centre grants (SONATA-BIS 2020/38/E/NZ3/00090 and SONATA 2021/43/D/NZ3/01798).

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

DISCLOSURE

The funding agency and institution S.A. is affiliated with was not involved in the contents of the manuscript.

REFERENCES:

1. Anbalagan S. Why do the majority of drugs fail in clinical trials? My search for a moksha in biology [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2024 May 14]; Available from: <https://zenodo.org/records/11079992>
2. Anbalagan S. Heme-based oxygen gasoreceptors. *Am J Physiol Endocrinol Metab* 2024; 326:E178–81.
3. Anbalagan S. Oxygen is an essential gasotransmitter directly sensed via protein gasoreceptors. *Animal Models and Experimental Medicine* 2024; 7:189–93.
4. Moreno-Domínguez A, Ortega-Sáenz P, Gao L, Colinas O, García-Flores P, Bonilla-Henao V, Aragonés J, Hüttemann M, Grossman LI, Weissmann N, et al. Acute O₂ sensing through HIF2 α -dependent expression of atypical cytochrome oxidase subunits in arterial chemoreceptors. *Sci Signal* 2020; 13:eaay9452.
5. Blyemehl K, Pérez-Gómez A, Omura M, Moreno-Pérez A, Macías D, Bai Z, Johnson RS, Leinders-Zufall T, Zufall F, Mombaerts P. A Sensor for Low Environmental Oxygen in the Mouse Main Olfactory Epithelium. *Neuron* 2016; 92:1196–203.
6. Goldberg MA, Dunning SP, Bunn HF. Regulation of the erythropoietin gene: evidence that the oxygen sensor is a heme protein. *Science* 1988; 242:1412–5.
7. Hochachka PW, Buck LT, Doll CJ, Land SC. Unifying theory of hypoxia tolerance: molecular/metabolic defense and rescue mechanisms for surviving oxygen lack. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 1996; 93:9493–8.
8. Sen Santara S, Roy J, Mukherjee S, Bose M, Saha R, Adak S. Globin-coupled heme containing oxygen sensor soluble adenylate cyclase in *Leishmania* prevents cell death during hypoxia. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 2013; 110:16790–5.
9. Middelhaufe S, Leipelt M, Levin LR, Buck J, Steegborn C. Identification of a haem domain in human soluble adenylate cyclase. *Biosci Rep* 2012; 32:491–9.
10. Tresguerres M, Levin LR, Buck J. Intracellular cAMP signaling by soluble adenylyl cyclase. *Kidney Int* 2011; 79:1277–88.
11. Beuve A. Conversion of a guanylyl cyclase to an adenylyl cyclase. *Methods* 1999; 19:545–50.
12. Mrnjavac N, Martin WF. GTP before ATP: The energy currency at the origin of genes [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2024 Jun 4]; Available from: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2403.08744>
13. Horst BG, Yokom AL, Rosenberg DJ, Morris KL, Hammel M, Hurley JH, Marletta MA. Allosteric activation of the nitric oxide receptor soluble guanylate cyclase mapped by cryo-electron microscopy. *Elife* 2019; 8:e50634.
14. Hess KC, Jones BH, Marquez B, Chen Y, Ord TS, Kamenetsky M, Miyamoto C, Zippin JH, Kopf GS, Suarez SS, et al. The “soluble” adenylyl cyclase in sperm mediates multiple signaling events required for fertilization. *Dev Cell* 2005; 9:249–59.

15. Keppner A, Correia M, Santambrogio S, Koay TW, Maric D, Osterhof C, Winter DV, Clerc A, Stumpe M, Chalmel F, et al. Androglobin, a chimeric mammalian globin, is required for male fertility. *eLife* 2022; 11:e72374.
16. Hoogewijs D, Ebner B, Germani F, Hoffmann FG, Fabrizius A, Moens L, Burmester T, Dewilde S, Storz JF, Vinogradov SN, et al. Androglobin: A Chimeric Globin in Metazoans That Is Preferentially Expressed in Mammalian Testes. *Molecular Biology and Evolution* 2012; 29:1105–14.